

A validated spectrophotometric analysis for simultaneous estimation of vincristine sulfate and bovine serum albumin in pure preparations using Vierordt's method

Hamid Jabbar Hasan¹, Mowafaq Mohammed Ghareeb²

¹ Oncology Teaching Hospital, Directorate of Medical City, Ministry of Health, Baghdad, Iraq

² Department of pharmaceuticals, College of Pharmacy, University of Baghdad, Baghdad, Iraq

Corresponding author: Mowafaq Mohammed Ghareeb (Mowafaq.abd@copharm.uobaghdad.edu.iq)

Received 25 March 2024 ♦ Accepted 18 June 2024 ♦ Published 5 August 2024

Citation: Hasan HJ, Ghareeb MM (2024) A validated spectrophotometric analysis for simultaneous estimation of vincristine sulfate and bovine serum albumin in pure preparations using Vierordt's method. *Pharmacia* 71: 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.71.e122621>

Abstract

The novel Vierordt's approach, or simultaneous equation method, was created and validated for the concurrent determination of vincristine sulfate (VCS) and bovine serum albumin (BSA) in pure solutions utilizing UV spectrophotometry. It is simple, precise, economical, rapid, reliable, and accurate. This method depends on measuring absorbance at two wavelengths, 296 nm and 278 nm, which correspond to the λ_{\max} of VCS and BSA in deionized water, respectively. The calibration curves of VCS and BSA are linear at concentration ranges of 10–60 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 200–1600 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, with correlation coefficient values (R^2) of 1 and 0.999, respectively. The limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) were 0.465 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 1.410 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for VCS and 41.096 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 124.533 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for BSA. The precision investigation indicated that the relative standard deviation (RSD) value was within limitations ($\text{RSD} < 2\%$). The percentage recovery varied between 99.40 and 103.20% for VCS and 97.90 and 102.54% for BSA at various concentration levels, demonstrating that the simultaneous equation technique is accurate. The suggested approach can be successfully applied to estimate VCS and BSA simultaneously in pure and pharmaceutical-marketed products comprising these two components.

Keywords

vincristine sulfate, bovine serum albumin, simultaneous equation method, UV spectroscopy

Introduction

VCS is a potent anticancer medication that belongs to a class of medicines known as vinca alkaloids. The VCS drug's anticancer mechanism is recognized to prevent cancer cell proliferation. As a result, it inhibits cancer growth and metastasis. VCS, marketed under the brand name Oncovin, is an antitumor medication commonly

used in combination with other drugs to treat various types of cancer, including Hodgkin's disease, leukemia, lung cancer, and brain cancer (Al-Musawi et al. 2021). Fig. 1 depicts the chemical structure of VCS.

BSA is commonly used as a model protein instead of human serum albumin (HSA) due to its similar structure. BSA, like HSA, comprises a single polypeptide chain, which contains 583 amino acid residues. The structure

Figure 1. The chemical structure of VCS.

is kept stable by 17 disulfide linkages connecting cysteine (Cys) amino acid residues. It possesses a molecular weight of about 66.8 kDa and a heart-shaped structure with three homologous domains I–III. Each domain comprises two unique subdomains, A and B, with distinct binding characteristics. BSA contains two tryptophan (Trp) amino acid residues, Trp-134 and Trp-212, at subdomains IB and IIA, respectively (Jahanban-Esfahlan et al. 2019). Fig. 2 shows the structure of albumin (Jahanban-Esfahlan et al. 2020).

Various nanocarriers have been created to enhance the efficacy or lessen the adverse effects of active medicinal substances, resulting in more efficient medication delivery. Protein-based nanoparticles (NPs) are becoming increasingly popular as drug delivery systems in clinical and research settings due to their high transport efficiency, biodegradability, non-immunogenicity, and nontoxicity. Albumin is an excellent choice for developing medication delivery systems, such as nanocarriers. In 2005, the US FDA authorized Abraxane, the albumin-bound form of paclitaxel. This product is the first example of a drug-loaded protein nanoparticle product to be successfully sold on the market (Luo et al. 2021).

Albumin can interfere with UV spectroscopy analysis of drugs as it absorbs light in the UV range (peptide bond at around 220 nm). This can lead to overlapping signals and make it difficult to measure the drug concentration accurately (Rasoulzadeh et al. 2010; Xu et al. 2013; Korkmaz et al. 2015).

A detailed literature search was conducted, and the results revealed that only a few analytical procedures, such as HPLC-UV (Rodrigues et al. 2009), UV (Bakmaz et al. 2021), RP-HPLC (Umrethia et al. 2010), UP-LC-MSMS (Yang et al. 2015), and HPLC (Stewart et al. 2021), have been reported for estimating VCS and BSA alone and in combination with other drugs. Numerous techniques have been previously reported for the analysis of vincristine in biological samples following the delivery of vincristine injection, ranging from HPLC-UV (Junping et al. 2003), HPLC combined with electrochemical detection technique (Gidding et al. 1999), to LC-MS (Schmidt et al. 2006), then to LC-MS/MS (Ling et al. 2010).

However, these test procedures are pretty complex; often, the mobile phases contain multiple components, and pH values must be adjusted. The last two approaches require MS equipment, which increases the test cost. Furthermore, the sample processing technique is more severe than the classic HPLC-UV technique to remove endogenous chemicals that may have an additive effect and hurt quantitative MS detection (Chen et al. 2011).

Embree et al. reported the analysis of VCS from human plasma following the administration of VCS liposome containing injection; the mobile phase was pretty complex, made up of diethylamine aqueous solution, acetonitrile, and methanol, and its pH value was adjusted to 7.0. In the present study, multiple mobile phases were employed to assess the concentration of VCS in the plasma specimens after the administration of its nanoparticle suspension. (Embree et al. 1997).

A recent literature review has found no UV spectrophotometric investigations of VCS and BSA in combined dosage form in pharmaceutical products. The current work aims to create a new spectrophotometric method that can be used for routine analysis in pharmaceutical companies, hospitals, and research laboratories. This method will estimate VCS and BSA in combined dosage form with reasonable accuracy, simplicity, precision, and economy over other chromatographic methods.

Figure 2. The HSA structure consists of three primary domains, I, II, and III; each one contains a pair of subdomains, known as A and B. Sites I and II, which are located in subdomains IIA and IIIA, respectively, are BSA's two critical binding sites.

Experimental

1. Materials and reagents

Vincristine sulfate and bovine serum albumin were purchased from Hangzhou Hyper Chemicals Limited, China. Deionized water was provided by Rafidain Environment Company, Iraq.

2. Instruments

Sensitive balance (Denver Instrument Germany), ultrasonic cleaner (Fuyang Technology China), hotplate magnetic stirrer (Joanlab/China), and two UV-visible spectrophotometers (double-beam Shimadzu-1900i/Japan and single-beam Shimadzu UVmini-1240/Japan) with UV probe software were utilized. Absorbance was measured with a pair of 1-cm-matched quartz cells.

3. Selection of a common solvent

Deionized water was chosen as a standard solvent for examining the spectrum properties of the selected compounds.

4. Preparation of typical stock solutions

A typical stock solution of VCS (100 µg/mL) was created by dissolving 10 mg using deionized water in a 100-mL volumetric flask. Sonication of the resulting solution was done for 5 minutes, followed by the volume adjustment to 100 mL with deionized water. From this typical stock solution, 6 mL was taken and diluted to 10 mL with deionized water to prepare a working standard solution of 60 µg/mL. Similarly, a typical stock solution of BSA (2000 µg/mL) was created by dissolving 200 mg using deionized water in a 100-mL volumetric flask. Sonication of the resulting solution was done for 10 minutes, followed by the volume adjustment to 100 mL with deionized water. From this typical stock solution, 8 mL was taken and diluted to 10 mL with deionized water to prepare a working standard solution of 1600 µg/mL (Giriraj and Sivakkumar 2014).

5. Determination of λ_{\max}

These working standard solutions (60 µg/mL for VCS and 1600 µg/mL for BSA) were scanned in the whole UV range (200–400 nm) to figure out the λ_{\max} . Absorption maxima of VCS and BSA were identified, and overlain spectra were recorded (Makvana and Sahoo 2019).

6. Preparation of calibration curves

Appropriate aliquots of each component were pipetted from the standard stock solutions into a series of 10-mL volumetric flasks, and the volume was filled up to the line with deionized water to get concentrations of 10–60 µg/mL of VCS and 200–1600 µg/mL of BSA. For each material, solutions of the series of concentrations were evaluated at

their corresponding wavelengths, and absorbance was measured (Bhaskar et al. 2020; Mohammed and Abed 2023).

7. Simultaneous equation method development

After plotting calibration curves to confirm Beer's law, the absorptivity values were calculated at the corresponding wavelength for each material, and these values were used to build the simultaneous equations, as illustrated below:

$$\text{At } \lambda_1: A_1 = ax_1bC_X + ay_1bC_Y \quad (1)$$

$$\text{At } \lambda_2: A_2 = ax_2bC_X + ay_2bC_Y \quad (2)$$

For measurements using cells of 1 cm, $b = 1$
Rearrangement of equation (2)

$$C_Y = A_2 - ax_2C_X / ay_2$$

Substitution of C_Y in equation (1) and rearrangement

$$C_X = A_2ay_1 - A_1ay_2 / ax_2ay_1 - ax_1ay_2 \quad (3)$$

$$C_Y = A_1ax_2 - A_2ax_1 / ax_2ay_1 - ax_1ay_2 \quad (4)$$

Where:

$\lambda_1 = 296$ nm and $\lambda_2 = 278$ nm

A_1 and A_2 are the absorbance at 296 nm and 278 nm respectively.

C_X and C_Y are the concentration of VCS and BSA, respectively.

ax_1 and ax_2 are the absorptivity of VCS at 296 nm and 278 nm, respectively.

ay_1 and ay_2 are the absorptivity of BSA at 296 nm and 278 nm, respectively.

The concentrations of both VCS and BSA in the sample solutions were calculated by utilizing two simultaneous equations (3) and (4) (Panchale et al. 2020).

8. Calculation of the absorptivity value

When the solutions of each material were scanned in triplicate versus the solvent blank at the designated wavelengths, the absorptivity of each solution was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Absorptivity, } A \text{ (1\%, 1 cm)} = \text{Absorbance at specified} \\ \text{wavelengths / concentration in g/100 mL} \quad (5)$$

(Begum et al. 2013).

9. Validation of the developed method

In method validation, International Conference of Harmonization (ICH) guidelines (Shabir 2005) recommendations for specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, ruggedness, robustness, stability, limits of detection, and quantification were carried out (Yaseen et al. 2023).

Specificity

Specificity is the ability to evaluate the analyte definitively in the presence of additional substances that are expected to be present (Ravisankar et al. 2015).

Specificity is investigated by the absorbance measurements of VCS and BSA at 296 nm and 278 nm, respectively, against the blank and the comparison of the absorbance of drug solutions with the blank (Venkatesan and Kannappan 2014).

Linearity

The linearity of VCS and BSA calibration graphs at their respective absorbance maxima was observed in the 10–60 µg/mL concentration ranges for VCS and 200–1600 µg/mL for BSA (Sakhare et al. 2016).

Accuracy

By definition, it is how close a measurement is to the accepted value. A recovery study using the standard addition method at three distinct levels (80%, 100%, and 120%) equal to 8/160, 10/200, and 12/240 mg of VCS/BSA, respectively, was performed to evaluate the accuracy of the proposed approaches. The percentage recovery by the intended method was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Recovery} = (A - B) / C \times 100 \quad (6)$$

Where:

A is the overall quantity of drug calculated (mg).

B is the quantity of drug present at the pre-analyzed level (mg).

C is the quantity of bulk drug added (mg) (Shetty and Patil 2014; Al-Momani and Al Souqi 2023).

Precision

The method's precision had been evaluated by checking its repeatability with intermediate precision. Repeatability is assessed with three replicates of the concentration of the analyte during one day at various intervals under identical experimental circumstances (intraday). The intermediate precision was examined by running the study on three distinct days with three replicates investigated each day (interday). The percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD) must be smaller than 2 (Abed and Hussein 2019; Al-Uzri et al. 2023).

After calculating the mean and standard deviation (SD), the relative standard deviation (RSD) is provided by the following equation:

$$\text{RSD} (\%) = \text{SD} \times 100 / \text{Mean} \quad (7)$$

(Solano-Cueva et al. 2023).

Ruggedness

Ruggedness is an investigation that was undertaken to study the impact of variation in analysts, labs, and instruments in triplicate measurements according to the experimental procedure (Venkatesan and Kannappan 2014).

Robustness

The robustness of an analytical technique is the capacity of an optimized approach to remain unaltered despite slight parameter variations. The robustness of the established UV technique was determined by altering the wavelength by (± 1 nm) and measuring the absorbance (Qureshi et al. 2021).

Stability

The stability study was tested by storing the drug solutions at room temperature for nine days, reading the absorbance of the sample solution each day, and checking for drug content (Giriraj and Sivakkumar 2017; Salih et al. 2018).

Sensitivity

LOD represents the minor concentration of a substance in the sample that can be reliably identified with the mentioned possibility, although it may not be quantified as a precise value. LOD is the same as "sensitivity," "analytical sensitivity," and "detection limit." LOQ is the minor concentration of analyte in the sample, which can be quantitatively determined under specified experimental conditions with sufficient precision and accuracy (Forootan et al. 2017).

Both the LOD and LOQ were calculated using the following equations:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma / S \quad (8)$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma / S \quad (9)$$

Where:

σ is the standard deviation of the intercept.

S is the slope (Mali et al. 2015; Habib et al. 2023).

Statistical analysis

The experiment data were presented as the mean of triplicate samples \pm standard deviation (Hussein and Rajab 2018).

Results and discussion

1. Determination of λ_{max}

The UV scanning showed a spectrum exhibiting λ_{max} of 296 nm and 278 nm for VCS and BSA, respectively, as shown in Fig. 3 (Jeewantha 2017; Malarkani et al. 2018).

2. Preparation of calibration curves

Calibration curves for VCS and BSA were constructed and shown in Figs 4, 5.

3. Simultaneous equation method development

Figs 6–8 illustrate the overlain spectra of both materials.

Figure 3. λ_{max} of BSA and VCS.

Figure 6. Overlain spectra of VCS.

Figure 4. Calibration curve of VCS in deionized water (10–60 µg/mL).

Figure 7. Overlain spectra of BSA.

Figure 5. Calibration curve of BSA in deionized water (200–1600 µg/mL).

Figure 8. Overlain spectra of VCS and BSA.

4. Determination of absorptivity value

Tables 1, 2 show the absorptivity values calculated for each concentration.

Table 1. Absorptivity values for VCS.

Concentration (µg/mL)	Absorbance λ_1-296	Absorptivity λ_1-296	Absorbance λ_2-278	Absorptivity λ_2-278
10	0.152	152.00	0.112	112.00
20	0.309	154.50	0.230	115.00
30	0.471	157.00	0.355	118.33
40	0.631	157.75	0.476	119.00
50	0.787	157.40	0.596	119.20
60	0.943	157.16	0.715	119.16
	Absorptivity for λ_1	155.986	Absorptivity for λ_2	117.115

Table 2. Absorptivity values for BSA.

Concentration (µg/mL)	Absorbance λ_1-296	Absorptivity λ_1-296	Absorbance λ_2-278	Absorptivity λ_2-278
200	0.023	1.15	0.113	5.65
400	0.043	1.07	0.235	5.87
600	0.067	1.11	0.358	5.96
800	0.089	1.11	0.486	6.07
1000	0.111	1.11	0.608	6.08
1200	0.138	1.15	0.736	6.13
1400	0.161	1.15	0.859	6.13
1600	0.180	1.12	0.971	6.06
	Absorptivity for λ_1	1.121	Absorptivity for λ_2	5.993

Validation of the developed method

Specificity and linearity

The specificity of the method was determined by calculating the absorbance of VCS and BSA separately at 296 nm and 278 nm against deionized water as a blank; their absorbance was compared with the blank. There was no interference at 296 nm or 278 nm, showing that the approach is specific. The calibration curves were linear in the concentration ranges from 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 to 60 µg/mL and 200, 400, 600, 800, 1000, 1200, 1400 to 1600 µg/mL for VCS and BSA, with correlation coefficient values (R^2) of 1 for VCS and 0.999 for BSA. Results revealed that a good correlation happens between the concentrations of the sample and their absorbance (Giriraj and Sivakkumar 2014).

Accuracy

Table 3 shows the results of calculating the quantity of VCS and BSA recovered at each level. The recovery tests were performed to ensure the technique's reproducibility and reliability. A known amount of the standard drugs was added to the pre-analyzed samples at three distinct levels (80%, 100%, and 120%). These

Table 3. Recovery results for VCS and BSA.

Concentration (%)	Added amount (mg)		Amount recovered (mg)		Amount recovered (%)	
	VCS	BSA	VCS	BSA	VCS	BSA
VCS/BSA						
80	8.00	160.00	17.952	356.640	99.40	97.90
100	10.00	200.00	20.320	405.096	103.20	102.54
120	12.00	240.00	22.014	435.720	100.86	98.21

Table 4. Intraday and interday precision results.

Parameters	Sampling time	VCS			BSA		
		Amount present (mg)	Amount present (%)	RSD (%)	Amount present (mg)	Amount present (%)	RSD (%)
Intraday precision	0 h	10.204	102.04 ± 0.09	0.90	206.432	103.21 ± 2.13	1.03
	1 st h	10.138	101.38 ± 0.18	1.82	207.338	103.67 ± 3.80	1.83
	2 nd h	10.036	100.36 ± 0.13	0.13	197.442	98.72 ± 1.38	0.70
Interday precision	1 st day	10.224	102.24 ± 0.13	1.33	200.025	100.01 ± 3.78	1.89
	2 nd day	9.956	99.56 ± 0.07	0.73	202.554	101.27 ± 2.28	1.28
	3 rd day	10.158	101.58 ± 0.07	0.75	207.726	103.86 ± 2.30	1.10

Table 5. Ruggedness results for VCS and BSA.

Parameters		VCS			BSA		
		Amount present (mg)	Amount present (%)	RSD (%)	Amount present (mg)	Amount present (%)	RSD (%)
Instrument	I						
Analyst	I	10.216	102.16 ± 0.19	1.06	209.277	104.63 ± 3.02	1.44
Analyst	II	10.266	102.66 ± 0.08	0.81	205.846	102.92 ± 3.98	1.93
Instrument	II						
Analyst	I	10.436	104.36 ± 0.14	1.41	210.177	105.08 ± 2.33	1.11
Analyst	II	10.254	102.54 ± 0.15	1.52	206.300	103.15 ± 2.45	1.19

Table 6. Results observed by altering the wavelength ± nm.

Wavelength (nm)	VCS			Wavelength (nm)	BSA		
	Amount present (mg)	Amount present (%)	RSD (%)		Amount present (mg)	Amount present (%)	RSD (%)
295	10.240	102.40 ± 0.17	1.72	277	215.268	107.63 ± 2.91	1.35
297	10.305	103.00 ± 0.90	0.92	279	208.886	104.44 ± 1.34	0.64

results indicate high accuracy, as the percent recoveries of the three concentrations were close to 100% (Sachin et al. 2014).

Precision

Table 4 shows the results of the percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD). The %RSD for intraday and interday precision for VCS and BSA was less than 2%, indicating a good level of precision (Chitlange et al. 2008).

Ruggedness

Table 5 shows the results of calculating the %RSD for each condition. The current procedure demonstrated good ruggedness when used by various analysts and instruments of the same make. The results are within acceptable limits, suggesting no substantial analyst-to-analyst or instrument-to-instrument variation and, therefore, the method's ruggedness (Donepudi and Achanta 2019).

Robustness

The results are presented in Table 6. A small change in the wavelength within (±1 nm) relative to the λ_{max} of VCS and BSA exhibited no influence, further indicating the validity of the created approach, with %RSD less than 2% falling within the permissible level (Ali and Elsaman 2021).

Stability

The results are presented in Table 7. The sample solution of VCS and BSA in deionized water is stable at room temperature without degradation for up to nine days (Giriraj and Sivakkumar 2017).

Table 7. Stability data for VCS and BSA.

Day	VCS		BSA	
	Amount present (mg)	Amount present (%)	Amount present (mg)	Amount present (%)
1	10.26	102.60	206.62	103.31
2	10.15	101.50	207.40	103.70
3	10.06	100.60	208.36	104.18
4	10.08	100.80	206.82	103.41
5	10.10	101.00	197.88	98.94
6	10.01	100.10	205.46	102.73
7	10.16	101.60	201.73	100.86
8	10.22	102.20	203.90	101.95
9	9.81	98.10	200.62	100.31

Sensitivity

The LOD and LOQ were computed theoretically for VCS and BSA and found to be 0.465 µg/mL, 1.410 µg/mL, 41.096 µg/mL, and 124.533 µg/mL, respectively.

Our study developed a simple, effective UV method to determine the concentration of VCS and BSA, with good accuracy and precision compared to the previously mentioned literature, which has used complex and time-consuming analytical procedures.

Conclusion

The created and validated UV estimating method described here is speedy, simple, accurate, sensitive, and

specific, with a lack of time in comparison with the HPLC analysis method, which needs preparation of the samples for analysis like extraction of solvent, degassing, and heating technique. This approach was also effectively applied to the quantitative calculation of VCS and BSA in combination dosage form. Thus, the disclosed method is critical and has wide application in the industry for quality control and assessment of VCS and BSA in mixed-dose forms.

Contribution of authors

The authors did this work mentioned in this article, and the authors will bear all liabilities pertaining to claims relating to the article's content. Hamid Jabbar Hasan achieved the experimental work in the study. Mowafaq Mohammed Ghareeb reviewed the article, provided comments on the study design, drafted the manuscript, and supervised this study.

Acknowledgments

The authors want to thank the University of Baghdad, College of Pharmacy, Department of Pharmaceutics, Iraq, for providing the required equipment, laboratories, devices, and support to accomplish the study.

The authors did not receive any sources of funding.

References

- Abed HN, Hussein AA (2019) Ex-vivo absorption study of a novel dabitran etexilate loaded nanostructured lipid carrier using non-everted intestinal SAC model. *Iraqi Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 28(2): 37–45. <https://doi.org/10.31351/vol28iss2pp37-45>
- Ali MS, Elsaman T (2021) Development and validation of the UV spectrophotometric method for simultaneous determination of paracetamol and pseudoephedrine in bulk and combined tablet dosage form. *Pharmaceutical Chemistry Journal* 54: 1306–1310. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11094-021-02360-w>
- Al-Momani IE, Al Souqi RI (2023) Indirect flow injection spectrophotometric and chromatographic methods for the determination of mebendazole in pharmaceutical formulations. *Baghdad Science Journal* 20: 1985–1991. <https://doi.org/10.21123/bsj.2023.6785>
- Al-Musawi S, Ibraheem S, Abdul Mahdi S, Albukhaty S, Haider AJ, Kadhim AA, Kadhim KA, Kadhim HA, Al-Karagoly H (2021) Smart nanoformulation based on polymeric magnetic nanoparticles and vincristine drug: a novel therapy for apoptotic gene expression in tumors. *Life* 11(1): 71. <https://doi.org/10.3390/life11010071>
- Al-Uzri WA, Jamal M, Hadi H (2023) Colorimetric determination of salbutamol sulfate using spectrophotometry-continuous flow injection technique in pure and pharmaceutical forms. *Iraqi Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 32(1): 45–52. <https://doi.org/10.31351/vol32iss1pp45-52>
- Bakmaz D, Ulu A, Koytepe S, Ates B (2021) Preparation, characterization, and in vitro release study of vincristine sulfate-loaded chitosan-polyethylene glycol-oleic acid composites. *International Journal of Polymer Analysis and Characterization* 26(4): 291–308. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1023666X.2021.1887624>
- Begum ASK, Basava RD, Rao RN (2013) Simultaneous estimation of rifampicin and isoniazid in combined dosage form by a simple UV spectrophotometric method. *Der Pharmacia Lettre* 5(3): 419–426. <http://scholarsresearchlibrary.com/archive.html>
- Bhaskar KL, Lakshmi D, Sumalatha G, Suji G, Kumar K (2020) Q-analysis and simultaneous equation method for estimation of domperidone and naproxen by UV spectrophotometry in bulk and tablet dosage form. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology* 13(12): 6050–6054. <https://doi.org/10.5958/0974-360X.2020.01054.9>
- Chen J, He H, Li S, Shen Q (2011) An HPLC method for the pharmacokinetic study of vincristine sulfate-loaded PLGA-PEG nanoparticle formulations after injection to rats. *Journal of Chromatography B* 879(21): 1967–1972. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2011.05.031>
- Chitlange SS, Imran M, Sakarkar D (2008) RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of amlodipine and metoprolol in tablet formulation. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutics (AJP)* 2(4): 232–234. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0973-8398.45037>
- Donepudi S, Achanta S (2019) Simultaneous estimation of saxagliptin and dapagliflozin in human plasma by validated high-performance liquid chromatography-ultraviolet method. *Turkish Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 16(2): 227. <https://doi.org/10.4274/tjps.galenos.2018.46547>

- Embree L, Gelmon KA, Tolcher AW, Hudon NJ, Heggie JR, Dedhar C, Webb MS, Bally MB, Mayer LD (1997) Validation of a high-performance liquid chromatographic assay method for quantification of total vincristine sulfate in human plasma following administration of vincristine sulfate liposome injection. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis* 16(4): 675–687. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0731-7085\(97\)00087-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0731-7085(97)00087-3)
- Forootan A, Sjöback R, Björkman J, Sjögreen B, Linz L, Kubista M (2017) Methods to determine limit of detection and limit of quantification in quantitative real-time PCR (qPCR). *Biomolecular Detection and Quantification* 12: 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bdq.2017.04.001>
- Gholve Sachin B, Asware Baburoo S, Kadam Shrihari C, Bhusnure Omprakash G, Thonte Sanjay S (2015) Development and validation of a simple UV spectrophotometric method for the determination of darunavir ethanolate both in bulk and marketed dosage formulations. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* 4(3): 1276–1283. <https://doi.org/10.7897/2230-8407.050467>
- Gidding CEM, Meeuwse-de Boer GJ, Koopmans P, Uges DRA, Kamps WA, De Graaf SSN (1999) Vincristine pharmacokinetics after repetitive dosing in children. *Cancer Chemotherapy and Pharmacology* 44: 203–209. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002800050968>
- Giriraj P, Sivakkumar T (2014) New simple spectrophotometric method for the simultaneous estimation of paracetamol and flupirtine maleate in pure and pharmaceutical dosage form. *International Journal of Spectroscopy* 2014(1): 968420. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/968420>
- Giriraj P, Sivakkumar T (2017) Simultaneous estimation of dutasteride and tamsulosin hydrochloride in tablet dosage form by vierordt's method. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry* 10: S1862–S1867. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2013.07.013>
- Habib NM, Al-Tameemi M, Tofah ML, Salman NK, Abdulkareem HM (2023) Spectrophotometric method combined with HPLC for bisphenol F determination in plastic bottled water and thermal paper. *Baghdad Science Journal* 20(1): 90–101. <https://doi.org/10.21123/bsj.2022.6821>
- Hussein ZA, Rajab NA (2018) Formulation and characterization of bromocriptine mesylate as liquid self-nano emulsifying drug delivery system. *Iraqi Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 27(2): 93–101. <https://doi.org/10.31351/vol27iss2pp93-101>
- Jahanban-Esfahlan A, Ostadrahimi A, Jahanban-Esfahlan R, Roufegarinejad L, Tabibiazar M, Amarowicz R (2019) Recent developments in the detection of bovine serum albumin. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 138: 602–617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2019.07.096>
- Jahanban-Esfahlan A, Roufegarinejad L, Jahanban-Esfahlan R, Tabibiazar M, Amarowicz R (2020) Latest developments in the detection and separation of bovine serum albumin using molecularly imprinted polymers. *Talanta* 207: 120317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2019.120317>
- Jeewantha HA, Ivanovich SA, Mihailovich KP (2017) Validated spectrophotometric method for the estimation of vincristine and vinblastine. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences* 9(4): 78–86. <https://doi.org/10.22159/ijpps.2017v9i4.16577>
- Junping W, Takayama K, Nagai T, Maitani Y (2003) Pharmacokinetics and antitumor effects of vincristine carried by microemulsions composed of PEG-lipid, oleic acid, vitamin E and cholesterol. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 251(1–2): 13–21. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5173\(02\)00580-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5173(02)00580-X)
- Korkmaz F, Erdogan DA, Özalp-Yaman Ş (2015) Interaction of a novel platinum drug with bovine serum albumin: FTIR and UV-Vis spectroscopy analysis. *New Journal of Chemistry* 39(7): 5676–5685. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5NJ00785B>
- Ling G, Zhang P, Zhang W, Sun J, Meng X, Qin Y, Deng Y, He Z (2010) Development of novel self-assembled DS-PLGA hybrid nanoparticles for improving oral bioavailability of vincristine sulfate by P-gp inhibition. *Journal of Controlled Release* 148(2): 241–248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2010.08.010>
- Luo H, Sheng J, Shi L, Yang X, Chen J, Peng T, Zhou Q, Wan J, Yang X (2021) Non-covalent assembly of albumin nanoparticles by hydroxyl radical: A possible mechanism of the nab technology and a one-step green method to produce protein nanocarriers. *Chemical Engineering Journal* 404: 126362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.126362>
- Makvana C, Sahoo S (2019) Spectrophotometric method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of nebivolol hydrochloride and valsartan in bulk and combined pharmaceutical dosage form in release media. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Drug Research* 11(6): 299–304. <https://doi.org/10.25004/IJPSDR.2019.110604>
- Malarkani K, Sarkar I, Selvam S (2018) Denaturation studies on bovine serum albumin–bile salt system: Bile salt stabilizes bovine serum albumin through hydrophobicity. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Analysis* 8(1): 27–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpha.2017.06.007>
- Mali AD, Mali S, Tamboli A, Bathe R (2015) Simultaneous UV spectrophotometric methods for estimation of metformin HCl and glimepiride in bulk and tablet dosage form. *International Journal of Advances in Pharmaceutics* 4(6): 117–124. <https://doi.org/10.7439/ijap>
- Mohammed FF, Abed SS (2023) Two spectrophotometric methods based on diazotization coupling reaction for determination of genistein in pure and supplement. *Iraqi Journal of Science* 64(4): 1581–1591. <https://doi.org/10.24996/ijis.2023.64.4.1>
- Panchale WA, Gulhane CA, Manwar JV, Bakal RL (2020) Simultaneous estimation of salbutamol sulphate and ambroxol HCl from their combined dosage form by UV-Vis spectroscopy using simultaneous equation method. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences* 13(3): 127–134. <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2020.13.3.0397>
- Qureshi HK, Veeresham C, Srinivas C (2021) Analytical method development and validation of etanercept by UV and RP-UFLC methods. *American Journal of Analytical Chemistry* 12(12): 493–505. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ajac.2021.1212031>
- Rasoulzadeh F, Asgari D, Naseri A, Rashidi MR (2010) Spectroscopic studies on the interaction between erlotinib hydrochloride and bovine serum albumin. *DARU Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 18(3): 179–184.
- Ravisankar P, Navya CN, Pravallika D, Sri DN (2015) A review of step-by-step analytical method validation. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy* 5(10): 7–19.
- Rodrigues AS, Lopes AR, Leão A, Couceiro A, Ribeiro ABS, Ramos F, da Silveira MIN, de Oliveira CR (2009) Development of an analytical methodology for simultaneous determination of vincristine and doxorubicin in pharmaceutical preparations for oncology by HPLC—UV. *Journal of Chromatographic Science* 47(5): 387–391. <https://doi.org/10.1093/chromsci/47.5.387>
- Sakhare RS, Pekamwar SS, Dhamane SD, Sujalegaonkar AG (2016) Development and validation of stability indicating assay method

- for simultaneous estimation of ilaprazole and domperidone in bulk and solid dosage form by UV-spectroscopy. *International Research Journal of Pharmacy* 7(9): 26–31. <https://doi.org/10.7897/2230-8407.079109>
- Salih ZT, Gawhari F, Rajab NA (2018) Preparation, release, rheology and stability of piroxicam emulgel. *International Journal of Applied Pharmaceutics* 10: 26–29. <https://doi.org/10.22159/ijap.2018v10i1.20234>
- Schmidt MS, Huang R, Classon RJ, Murry DJ (2006) Determination of vincristine in infant plasma by liquid chromatography-atmospheric pressure chemical ionization-mass spectroscopy. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis* 41(2): 540–543. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2005.11.039>
- Shabir GA (2005) Step-by-step analytical methods validation and protocol in the quality system compliance industry. *Journal of Validation Technology* 10: 314–325.
- Shetty PR, Patil DD (2014) Applications of simultaneous equation method and derivative method for the determination of rabeprazole sodium and levosulpiride in pharmaceutical dosage form and dissolution samples. *Journal of the Association of Arab Universities for Basic and Applied Sciences* 15(1): 53–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaubas.2013.05.005>
- Solano-Cueva N, Figueroa JG, Loja C, Armijos C, Vidari G, Ramírez J (2023) A Validated HPLC-UV-ESI-IT-MS method for the quantification of carnosol in *Lepechinia mutica*. A Medicinal Plant Endemic to Ecuador. *Molecules* 28(18): 6701. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28186701>
- Stewart SA, Waite D, Domínguez-Robles J, McAlister E, Permana AD, Donnelly RF, Larrañeta E (2021) HPLC method for levothyroxine quantification in long-acting drug delivery systems. Validation and evaluation of bovine serum albumin as levothyroxine stabilizer. *Journal of Pharmaceutical And Biomedical Analysis* 203: 114182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2021.114182>
- Umrethia M, Kett VL, Andrews GP, Malcolm RK, Woolfson AD (2010) Selection of an analytical method for evaluating bovine serum albumin concentrations in pharmaceutical polymeric formulations. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis* 51(5): 1175–1179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2009.12.004>
- Venkatesan S, Kannappan N (2014) Simultaneous spectrophotometric method for determination of emtricitabine and tenofovir disoproxil fumarate in three-component tablet formulation containing rilpivirine hydrochloride. *International Scholarly Research Notices* 2014(1): 541727. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/541727>
- Xu H, Yao N, Xu H, Wang T, Li G, Li Z (2013) Characterization of the interaction between eupatorin and bovine serum albumin by spectroscopic and molecular modeling methods. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 14(7): 14185–14203. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms140714185>
- Yang F, Wang H, Hu P, Jiang J (2015) Validation of an UPLC-MS-MS method for quantitative analysis of vincristine in human urine after intravenous administration of vincristine sulfate liposome injection. *Journal of Chromatographic Science* 53(6): 974–978. <https://doi.org/10.1093/chromsci/bmu164>
- Yaseen A, Ghareeb MM, Alsaffar DF, Ming TS, Gazzali AM (2023) Development and validation of HPLC method for the detection of fusidic acid loaded in non-ionic and cationic nanoemulsion-based gels. *Biomedical and Pharmacology Journal* 16(1): 573–580. <https://doi.org/10.13005/bpj/2639>